

SHERPA
Rural Science-Society-Policy
Interfaces

MAP Position Paper

CHANGE IN PRODUCTION AND DIVERSIFICATION OF THE RURAL ECONOMY

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Authors

Nordregio | Louise Ormstrup Vestergård and Karen Refsgaard

Contributors

The participants in Multi-Actor Platform (MAP) Denmark

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Find out more about the Danish Multi-Actor Platform!
<https://rural-interfaces.eu/maps/denmark>

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Thank you to the Rural Council of Denmark and Sustainable Herning for hosting MAP Denmark's physical meetings in 2021. When the first meetings in MAP Denmark were to take place in spring 2020, they had to move online due to the corona pandemic. Therefore, it was of special importance for the collaboration and work in MAP Denmark to meet in person at the Rural Council of Denmark in Odder, June 2021, and again in Herning at Sustainable Herning, September 2021.

The composition of MAP Denmark is dynamic. At the start, the Rural Council of Denmark and the Danish Agriculture and Food Council contributed to identify members of MAP Denmark. Later, other members have contributed with additional suggestions to cover more perspectives and areas.

The organisations represented in MAP Denmark in 2021 divided by group are:

Research

- Center for Regional and Tourism Research
- Danish Centre for Rural Research, University of Southern Denmark
- Department of People and Technology, Roskilde University

Society

- Rural Council of Denmark
- Danish Agriculture and Food Council
- The Association of Danish Small Islands
- Balance Denmark
- Sustainable Herning
- Collective Impact
- Landbo Ungdom (Rural youth organisation)
- Think tank Frej
- The Danish society for Nature Conservation

Policy

- The Housing and Plan Agency
- The Agricultural Agency
- Central Denmark Region
- Svendborg municipality
- Lejre municipality
- Guldborgsund municipality

To learn more about the SHERPA project please visit: <https://rural-interfaces.eu/>

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Topic and headline messages from MAP Denmark

- MAP Denmark has identified six themes that are central to changing production and diversifying the rural economy in a Danish context: 1) green transition, 2) education and competencies, 3) liveability, 4) entrepreneurship, 5) financing and 6) digitalisation.
- MAP Denmark agrees that several key dimensions are missing in a Danish context in relation to those identified in the SHERPA Discussion Paper. These include: rural settlement, services, funding, competencies and education, attractive living conditions and communities.
- In order to stimulate successful and efficient rural development and a strong economy in Denmark, initiatives addressing the six highlighted themes need to be linked.
- The green transition will go a long way towards bringing rural areas back into focus by providing a range of opportunities that will contribute to reduced greenhouse-gas emissions, increased biodiversity, economic diversification and job creation. Many of these are linked to the use of local biological and land resources, as well as to the local competencies needed for managing them. It includes new production and solutions within agriculture, circular processes and new company structures within the new bioeconomy.
- The green transition entails huge investments in rural areas that can contribute to rural development if they are a part of a co-ordinated effort. If not, the increasing number of initiatives to address the situation in rural areas will lead to greater polarisation of Danish society and rural areas will end up as the loser.
- A holistic, long-term and multifunctional approach to land use and greenfield planning is necessary to achieve the goals of the green transition and create accessible and liveable rural areas.
- It would be worthwhile to revise the Planning Act and address other conditions to secure that they are adapted to the structure and potential of rural areas.
- Creating attractive living conditions and promoting communities and social capital are important prerequisites for supporting the development of the rural economy.
- Access to financing is crucial for rural areas, and the polarisation of the housing market must be addressed.
- Digital infrastructure is a sine qua non.

Problem being addressed and key questions

MAP Denmark highlights six themes central to a discussion of changing production and diversifying the economy in rural areas in Denmark. The themes, shown in Figure 1, are: the green transition, education and competencies, liveability, entrepreneurship, financing and digitalisation.

In addition to the four themes highlighted in the SHERPA Discussion Paper (entrepreneurship, employment and new business models; digitalisation and smartness; farm diversification; and the rural response to climate change and bioeconomy)¹, the members of MAP Denmark have added three themes that are important in the Danish context: liveability; financialisation; and education and competencies. Farm diversification and the rural response to climate change and the bioeconomy are represented under the green-transition theme.

Figure 1: Identification of themes.

The work of MAP Denmark

MAP Denmark held two physical meetings in 2021. During the first meeting, in June, the work was based on the SHERPA Discussion Paper and involved a discussion of the challenges, opportunities and key themes in the Danish context. After the meeting, all MAP members were asked to contribute their insights from relevant studies, reports and good case examples to the position paper. A draft of MAP Denmark's Position Paper based on the contributions and discussions from the first meeting was prepared by the facilitator and monitor for MAP Denmark. The draft was sent to the MAP members before the second meeting, in September. During the meeting, we discussed the main messages of each theme, lack of perspectives and in which areas more research is needed. A finished draft was circulated to all members of MAP Denmark in October for a final review before publication.

The first meeting was attended by ten MAP members; the second by nine. The facilitator and monitor for the MAP were present at both.

The key questions addressed for each dimension are:

- 1) What are the key needs for the development of the rural economy in your MAP, and how can they be addressed most effectively? Are the four dimensions of diversification identified in the SHERPA Discussion Paper also relevant in Denmark, or should other dimensions be added?
- 2) How can policy interventions support positive changes in the diversification of the rural economy, considering solutions that are needed at the local and national levels, and any implications for the wider policy framework (European Union level or others)? What can public administrations (at all levels) do to facilitate and encourage positive changes in the diversification of the rural economy?
- 3) What are the research needs and gaps?

¹ https://rural-interfaces.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/SHERPA_DiscussionPaper-diversification.pdf

1. Green transition

According to the EU's Green Deal², a fair green transition refers to the transition towards a climate-neutral economy that leaves no-one behind. The same understanding of the green transition is central to the Nordic Vision³, which is based on the assumption that the region's economy can continue to grow, and that social inclusion can be strengthened without depleting resources or spoiling the environment. In this transition, activities that are heavily dependent on fossil fuels will be gradually phased out or replaced by other technologies. Finally, there are new types of activities and development that are competitive, and which are suitable for rural areas. Here, bioeconomy and circular economy, which is based on the renewable biological resources of the land and the waters of rural areas, is highly relevant. Denmark has a long history of using agricultural resources biologically as well as institutionally, while new processes, new products and new forms of organisation of bioeconomic and circular-economic activities are rapidly developing.

Below are the areas that MAP Denmark has highlighted as particularly important for the green transition.

1.1. Key scientific evidence

Reduced greenhouse gas emissions

In June 2020, a new climate act came into force in Denmark⁴. The act makes the climate goal of reducing greenhouse-gas emissions by 70% (compared with 1990 levels) by 2030 and a goal of climate neutrality in 2050 part of Danish legislation. The Council on Climate Change (an independent expert body tasked with advising the government on the transition to a climate-neutral society) must provide an annual assessment of the progress towards achieving the goal. In the latest status report, published in February 2021, the Council on Climate Change concluded that the government's efforts are not sufficient for reaching the Climate Act's target of a 70% reduction by 2030, and that new initiatives will be required (Council on Climate Change 2021).

In order to meet the ambitious climate targets, all sectors of the economy must undergo a transformation. This includes major areas of economic activity, such as agriculture, energy, transport, construction and industry. In October 2021, a majority of the Folketing (the national assembly) agreed to measures to reduce greenhouse-gas emissions from agriculture 55-65% by 2030, to reduce nitrogen emissions, as well as for investments in technologies that will contribute to the green transition of agriculture⁵. At the same time, it is the vision of the Danish Food and Agriculture Council (a lobby group) for the Danish food industry to be climate neutral by 2050; the first milestone towards reaching this goal is to reduce emissions by 50% (measured from 1990 to 2030).

Land use

Accelerating the pace at which carbon-rich lowland soils are removed from use as cropland and restored as wetlands is a key element of the Council on Climate Change's recommendations for enabling the realisation of the 70% target, and it is a part of the Folketing's resolution. It is also an area that the Danish Agriculture Agency works with, particularly in the context of multifunctional land distribution (described below), which has as its goal to use land redistribution to accommodate such things as watercourses, biodiversity, reversing nature fragmentation, forestation and rural development. However, use of this tool by national authorities has met with criticism from affected communities for rigidly hewing to certain criteria, such as financing and the conditions that exist naturally (Christensen 2021). Collective Impact, an eight-year project supported by

² https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

³ <https://www.norden.org/sv/var-vision-2030>

⁴ <https://kefm.dk/Media/1/D/aftale-om-klimalov-af-6-december-2019%20FINAL-a-webtilg%C3%A6ngelig.pdf>

⁵ <https://fm.dk/media/25215/aftale-om-groen-omstilling-af-dansk-landbrug.pdf>

Realdania (a charity that provides funding for architecture and planning) is working on how to methodically support multifunctional land distribution using a method of the same name: collective impact. The basic idea is that complex societal changes require dialogue and interaction between many stakeholders in relation to a common goal⁶.

Danish studies of holistic planning show that landowners' rationale is of crucial social significance for how they and their lands can be involved in holistic planning processes (Kristensen et al., 2015; J. Primdahl et al., 2019). This will be of great importance in the future, when greenfield planning can be expected to become more prominent in relation to everything from climate protection, removal of lowland soils from production, land reform and reductions in carbon-dioxide emissions to biodiversity and new forms of settlement. Early involvement of the local population in connection with changed land use is considered to be highly important if the green transition is to have buy-in amongst communities. A study of the local impact of new forms of ownership that looks at, amongst other things, how to achieve various synergies when pursuing environmental and nature goals and in rural development can be found in Broegaard, Larsen & Hedetoft (2021).

The potential of the bioeconomy and the circular economy

Overall, the food industry (which here includes agriculture, fisheries, food companies and agribusiness) employed some 189,000 people in Denmark in 2019⁷. However, the distribution varies considerably by municipality; in a number of rural and outlying municipalities the proportion of food-industry employees approaches 10% of the workforce. The traditional agricultural complex currently accounts for 125,000 jobs, a number that shrunk 15% between 2007 and 2020⁸. At the same time, there are more jobs related to bioeconomy and circular economy. Studies by Nordregio show there was a 16% increase in these types of jobs in Denmark between 2008 and 2017 (Refsgaard et al. 2020). These studies include new products (such as biogas, grass proteins and bioplastics) and services (such as stores selling second-hand textiles and recreational activities in rural and forest areas). Traditional agriculture, forestry and fisheries activities are also still highly important for this development, given that they contribute the key resources needed for these new processes, products and services.

There is already a growing focus on Danish agricultural enterprises increasing production of plants for human consumption and reducing production of animal products. If successful, this will lead to new types of value chains and green jobs in rural areas. An example is the Agrifoodture⁹ project, which promotes the development of an industry that produces plant products for human consumption. The project is supported by Innovation Fund Denmark (a nationally backed investment fund) and includes the participation of firms representing all parts of food value chain, as well as academics, lobby groups, investors and more. The project estimates that Denmark can produce plant-based food for 1-3% of the global market.

The green transition is highly visible in bioeconomy, where it drives new forms of co-operation and new ways of processing green resources for use as products and services. These resources include organic waste from manufacturers, agricultural producers and cities, as well as biogas and other forms of energy. In terms of services, it includes circular utilisation of biological residue to produce feed, textiles and energy. Other applications include using biological resources to make high-quality medicines, food and related products. A final use is the conversion of renewable energy to high-quality fuels for use by planes, heavy ground-transport vehicles and ships. GreenLab Skive is one such example of an industrial symbiosis involving renewable energy and collaboration between various stakeholders on a common platform (see case description below).

⁶ <https://collectiveimpact.dk/>

⁷ <https://lf.dk/viden-om/beskaeftigelse>

⁸ <https://www.statistikbanken.dk/20096>

⁹ [https://pure.au.dk/portal/da/persons/joergen-e-olesen\(d3bcf85c-a32d-4169-8f78-b2bf7fe78102\)/publications/agrifoodture-roadmap-for-sustainable-transformation-of-the-danish-agrifood-system\(cbb0dc09-460f-4e37-a43e-322847057641\).html](https://pure.au.dk/portal/da/persons/joergen-e-olesen(d3bcf85c-a32d-4169-8f78-b2bf7fe78102)/publications/agrifoodture-roadmap-for-sustainable-transformation-of-the-danish-agrifood-system(cbb0dc09-460f-4e37-a43e-322847057641).html)

Ownership and financialisation of agricultural land

Investment in agricultural land has been on the increase in Denmark, Europe and the world in recent years. Unfortunately, there are no statistics detailing how much land is in the hands of external owners, although in 2020 Statistics Denmark (the national statistics bureau) compiled an inventory of foreign owners, and Hansen et al. (2021) has prepared a report looking into “tomorrow’s ownership forms” in Danish agriculture. Finally, an attempt has been made to quantify investor owners and investor-owned properties in a recent study of the local impact of new forms of ownership in Danish agriculture (see Broegaard et al. 2021). The structural development can nevertheless be read to some extent in figures from Statistics Denmark: from 2010 to 2020, the number of agricultural properties fell by more than 20%, from some 42,000 to 33,000. At the same time, the number of farms larger than 400ha doubled, from 642 to 1,216. Of the 33,000 farms, the proportion of sole proprietorships declined by 10,000, while there has been an increase in the number of farms owned by other types of owners. See^{10, 11}.

There are few studies of the local effects of external ownership of land, but a recent Danish study that includes case studies concludes in line with previous research in the field that the investment rationale (the purpose of the investment) determines the effects locally (Broegaard, Larsen and Hedetoft 2021). If the investment is a financialisation of agricultural land, there is typically no focus on things like socially beneficial agriculture or rural development. New forms of ownership in agriculture such as national or local agricultural funds often do have stated environmental goals, however, just as they have goals for nature, generational renewal and rural development. Representatives of these agricultural funds or working boards get involved in things like the diversification of sales channels, which helps increase the earnings of primary producers. Attracting residents who are interested in rural life and have a job or business they are enthusiastic about is essential to creating liveable rural communities. For a community, it makes a difference if a house is rented out to someone who is employed temporarily at a large farm or if it is inhabited by a person or a family who see themselves as part of the community for many years to come and therefore is engaged and active locally.

There are also several examples of very small farms that have successfully maintained employment levels by diversifying their products, planting high-value crops and by taking part in the experience economy (Bornholm: Broegaard, 2021; Samsø: Larsen, 2021). The latter, in particular, makes a valuable contribution to place branding (Broegaard, et al 2021).

External ownership of agricultural land as well as the structural development towards ever-larger agricultural holdings reinforces, according to Broegaard et al. (2021), a development pattern in which rural areas are emptied of their populations and even villages close to large provincial towns begin to feel run down as farms and houses become vacant or are rented out to temporary tenants who do not have the same commitment to the community as people who have made an active choice to move there and settle permanently.

CAP reform 2023-2027

At the EU level, the negotiation of a CAP reform for 2023-2027 means that 25% of the total grant within Pillar 1 (direct hectare support) will go to the Ecoschemes axis (green initiatives that promote the environment, climate and biodiversity). Ecoschemes are an incentive to provide financial support to those who voluntarily implement additional environmental measures. It has not yet been decided how much in total will have to be moved from Pillar 1 to Pillar 2. In addition, 3% will be set aside to support generational renewal. This is compared with 2% of the total EU subsidy previously^{12, 13}. In Denmark, the government plans to redistribute some 2 billion kroner between farms.

¹⁰ <https://www.statistikbanken.dk/statbank5a/selectvarval/saveselections.asp>

¹¹ <https://www.statistikbanken.dk/statbank5a/selectvarval/saveselections.asp>

¹² <https://lf.dk/-/media/lf/aktuelt/publikationer/lf/2021/vaerd-at-vide-om-landbrugsstoetten.pdf>

¹³ https://lbt.dk/fileadmin/user_upload/NaturErhverv/Filer/Styrelsen/Om_styrelsen/Landbrugsseminarer/2020/Til_hjemmeside_-_Oplaeg_PP_til_landbrugsseminar_-_CAP2020_FINAL.pdf

The Danish Food and Agriculture Council has calculated that the effect of CAP 2023 and the government's proposals will span from a gain of 50,000 kroner per farm to a loss of 1,600,000 kroner per farm. This has led it to take the position that a green transformation of the food industry is not realistic without public-sector funding. The industry notes that energy producers have received hundreds of billions of kroner for their conversion and the transport industry 25 billion kroner.

Cases

Multifunctional land distribution as a tool¹⁴

Multifunctional land distribution involves the purchase and sale of land to make multifunctional projects possible. In multifunctional projects, continued agricultural production does not run counter to goals such as biodiversity, reduced greenhouse-gas emissions, climate adaptation, cleaner aquatic environments, improved outdoor recreation opportunities and rural development.

During multifunctional land distribution, cropland is left fallow and allowed to grow wild, improving the state of the environment and making it easier for people to experience greenfield locations. Land redistribution is complicated; all of an area's landowners must buy and sell land with each other concurrently. Landowners who give up cropland are offered land elsewhere that can be farmed, and, for all participating landowners, the goal is to consolidate their fields in larger contiguous blocks or to be offered more productive cropland.

Multifunctional land distribution requires the collaboration of the municipality, community groups and landowners. During the redistribution, municipalities will have the opportunity to realise plans for nature protection, the environment and outdoor recreational activities. For community groups, it is an opportunity to realise ideas that benefit the community and to develop rural areas. Local landowners, meanwhile, will have the opportunity to see land used for agriculture or forestry included in environmental-protection projects, while in exchange being offered plots of land closer to other plots of land they own, potentially reducing their operational costs.

For multifunctional land distribution to work, it must be done voluntarily (no land can change ownership unless the owner agrees to take part) and the project must involve the participation all parties.

An example where multifunctional land distribution has been approved and is ongoing is Nørreådal, in Viborg municipality.¹⁵

BioScape — a biodiversity project in the Central Denmark Region¹⁶

With an expected budget of 37 million kroner, the BioScape biodiversity project will incorporate three pilot areas in the Central Denmark Region to show how the reorganisation of agricultural and other land can benefit landowners, biodiversity, the environment and efforts to address climate degradation. The project period runs from October 2021 to October 2026.

The on-going climate and biodiversity crisis requires that we, as a society — both globally and locally — come up with new ways to use our land. Literally as well as figuratively. As many as seven of the 17 UN Sustainable Development Goals relate to land use, and agriculture naturally has an impact on carbon emissions, food production, drinking water and how increased precipitation is managed. For this reason, the

¹⁴ Description obtained at: <https://lbst.dk/landbrug/arealer-og-ejendomme/jordfordeling/multifunktionel-jordfordeling-mufjo/hvad-er-multifunktionel-jordfordeling/>. Accessed 15 Sep 2021

¹⁵<https://viborg.dk/demokrati-og-indflydelse/udvikling-og-planer/udvikling/vi-udvikler-natur-og-klimaprojekter/jordfordeling-i-noerreaadalen-ved-oerum/>

¹⁶ Description obtained at: <https://www.rm.dk/om-os/aktuelt/nyheder/nyheder-2021/september-21/nyt-partnerskab-viser-vei-til-nytankning-af-land-arealer/>. Accessed on 17 Sep 2021

Central Denmark Region, together with eight partners, has undertaken the BioScape multifunctional land distribution project.

By working closely with participating landowners (all of whom are doing so voluntarily), the project seeks to use the three focus areas to show how climate and biodiversity challenges can be addressed through measures such as using land for new purposes. These measures will preferably address several goals at the same time, be it wetland re-establishment, carbon storage, increased biodiversity or improved recreational value.

The Central Denmark Region, the municipalities of Lemvig, Horsens and Hedensted, SEGES (an agricultural think tank), the Danish Society for Nature Conservation, Aarhus University, SAMN Forsyning A/S (a water and sewerage company) and the European Landowners Organisation (a lobby group) are participating in the project.

BioScape's three pilot areas are: Byn Lake, in Lemvig; Endelave Island, in Horsens; and Åstrup Fen, in Hedensted. The project's activities all involve multiple project areas. One of the goals of the project is to give the participating municipalities the opportunity to exchange experiences and help each other with specific initiatives. The first public BioScape activities will take place in October 2021.

GreenLab Skive

Located in Skive municipality, GreenLab is a green and circular energy park for green companies that will contribute to the green transition. The companies are connected to a SymbiosisNet™ of sustainable energy resources that are part of a smart network based on wind, solar and biogas. SymbiosisNet™ allows companies to share their surplus energy, which helps to improve cost efficiency. A Power2X plant that will utilise electrolysis production is under construction. When complete, it will contribute green hydrogen and oxygen to industrial processes and electric fuels.

Bioeconomy is a central part of the business models and expansion of the value chain for biomass. It involves resources from both the sea and land for use in the production of nutrients, protein feed and biogas. Plastic waste is converted into high-quality oil and chemical products.

Organisationally, GreenLab is a public-private consortium whose members include firms and universities from Denmark and abroad. Skive municipality is the owner of the area and serves as landlord. The partnership, the network between its stakeholders and the combined focus on bioeconomy and Power2X are the foundations for a business model for green transformation that is realisable and profitable and can contribute to the community financially, as well as in the form of jobs and environmentally friendly solutions^{17, 18}.

1.2. Summary of position of MAP Denmark

The green transition is associated with opportunities and challenges when it comes to reducing greenhouse-gas emissions, diversifying the economy and creating new jobs in rural areas. According to MAP Denmark, these include:

- Development of solutions in the existing bioeconomy that are linked to agricultural production, including:
 - Production of proteins based on grass as an alternative to imported proteins for Danish livestock production.
 - Modified feeding to reduce methane emissions.
 - Production of new crops for human consumption.
 - Development of biochar to improve agricultural soil and increase its capacity to store carbon.

¹⁷ <https://www.greenlab.dk/>

¹⁸ <https://pub.norden.org/nord2020-001/#78769>

- Streamlined agricultural operations, including new barn technologies, breeding and genetic development; conversion of manure for energy; fuel, manure and carbon sequestration with biogas and pyrolysis: reduced nutrient load through, amongst other things, precision agriculture; and the setting-aside and reforestation of marginal land.
 - Altered forms of cultivation, such as the introduction of crops with a smaller climate footprint.
 - An agricultural organisation that sets its own goals for addressing climate degradation and improving biodiversity, in so doing showing the good intentions of agriculture and its willingness to enter into a dialogue with the community.
- Identification and incorporation of local potentials and strengths
 - Prioritisation of activities within the new bioeconomy, focusing in particular on new circular company structures and new processes for bio-resources, such as:
 - production of energy from biogas, solar, wind etc.
 - converting industrial and household waste into new products.
 - establishment of Power2X systems.
 These activities require land as well as the establishment of major infrastructure and new forms of private-public co-operation in rural areas. In these types of projects, local ownership^{19,20}, not just local support, is necessary to guarantee acceptance.
 - MAP Denmark believes it is extremely important to ensure that the green transition contributes growth, jobs and educational opportunities to rural areas. This is contingent upon changed structures for forms of ownership of the new company structures through the establishment of local apprenticeship positions that draw upon local resources in collaboration with local companies.
 - Land use is increasingly in focus, and it has many stakeholders. Throughout much of history, land has primarily been an agricultural asset and used for food production. This has resulted in a body of legislation, such as the Planning Act. Today, there are more stakeholders taking an interest in how land is used.
 - Multifunctional land distribution is an example of how to seek solutions that satisfy multiple interests^{21,22} through outcomes such as consolidation of plots of cropland, increased biodiversity, better access to recreational areas for the local population, as well as contributions to a more attractive settlement structure. This, however, is a demanding and inflexible process in which rural development is not included to a significant degree.
 - MAP Denmark therefore recommends a holistic approach to land use that takes into account the various interests in an inclusive manner, and which balances economic, social and environmental considerations.

As a follow-up to these opportunities and related challenges, MAP Denmark highlights the following areas for further study:

- There is a need to identify and study topics of conflict and to identify where the major land use challenges are, what conflicts and opportunities exist and how multifunctional land distribution can contribute positively to the individual stakeholders and the three bottom lines. At the same time,

¹⁹ <https://www.greenlab.dk/>

²⁰ <https://www.bornholmshavvind.dk/>

²¹ [https://pure.au.dk/portal/en/publications/agrifoodture-roadmap-for-sustainable-transformation-of-the-danish-agrifood-system\(cbb0dc09-460f-4e37-a43e-322847057641\).html](https://pure.au.dk/portal/en/publications/agrifoodture-roadmap-for-sustainable-transformation-of-the-danish-agrifood-system(cbb0dc09-460f-4e37-a43e-322847057641).html)

²² <https://www.jaaktuelt.dk/momentum/2021/nr-3/>

there is a need for improved processes and guidance in implementing the processes to ensure inclusion and involvement.

- It is necessary to study local employment and local economic growth (which industries and which areas) and how the green transition can contribute to rural development.
- There is a need for an evaluation of how greenhouse-gas emissions are calculated and an implementation of more reliable studies that take into account all emissions from either production or consumption. This also includes studying production and processes in the green transition.

2. Education and competencies

2.1. Key scientific evidence

Education can be considered the pipeline that feeds the local and regional labour market because the vast majority of school leavers stay in the area where they studied. This means that as education in Denmark has coalesced around the four main cities, the educational system has come to cater first and foremost to the labour market in these cities. One of the consequences of this is that it has become difficult for a lot of companies located outside these cities to recruit skilled employees. Similarly, efforts to attract new residents to areas outside of the main cities as well as to promote growth are hamstrung by an inability to attract people to fill positions, such as teacher, nurse, doctor and childcare professional, that are crucial for a society — regardless of its size — to function.

Political action to change in the educational system

A broad majority in the Folketing passed legislation²³ at the end of June 2021 that will establish educational institutions, with a total enrolment in the thousands, outside of the four main cities.

The parties that supported the legislation said they wished to avoid a situation in which young people's opportunities in life were determined by whether they lived in one of the four main cities or whether they lived elsewhere. The parties also stated that good educational opportunities benefit not just Danish society as a whole but also communities that are economically depressed, suffer from out-migration and lack people with the types of skills that these educational institutions will teach. Furthermore, the aim of spreading educational opportunities throughout the country was seen as a way to accommodate young people who have neither the interest nor the resources to move to a major city; establishing educational institutions outside of the four main cities provides these young people with the opportunity to get an education closer to where they are from. The parties supporting the legislation further underscored that it was vital for companies throughout Denmark to have access to qualified labour. Decentralising educational institutions will be a way to encourage this. "Therefore, there is a great need for skilled workers in all parts of the country. This is true for professional and vocational skills. It is true for maritime and technical skills. And it is true for specialised, university-level competencies. Just as it is true for the social-service skills needed at the national, municipal and regional level," the legislation states.

To begin with, the legislation calls for the establishment of 23 new educational programmes outside the four main cities²⁴. At the same time, it mandates the expansion of enrolment for existing social-services training

²³ <https://ufm.dk/lovstof/politiske-aftaler/aftale-om-flere-og-bedre-uddannelsesmuligheder-i-hele-danmark/politisk-aftale-om-rammerne-for-flere-og-bedre-uddannelsesmuligheder-i-hele-danmark.pdf>

²⁴ <https://ufm.dk/aktuelt/pressemeddelelser/2021/filer/Kort.jpg>

programmes outside the four main cities by a total of 1,000, as well as a reduction in enrolment by 1,000 in existing social-service training programmes in the four main cities and the resources transferred to programmes elsewhere. The legislation also establishes an enrolment drawdown target of 5-10% by 2030 for educational institutions in the four main cities. By the spring of 2022, educational institutions need to have prepared a comprehensive plan for where educational programmes will be relocated to. The plan must detail how the goal of relocating or drawing down uptake by 10% can be achieved by 2030.

Amongst the legislation's other stipulations is an increase in the amount of per-student funding educational institutions outside the four main cities receive. The amount is to be increased by 5% in 2023 and 7% in 2027, while the rate for educational institutions in the four main cities is to remain unchanged. At the same time, the parties have agreed to double primary funding for decentralised educational programmes to 4 million kroner annually and to 2 million kroner for satellite programmes.

Vocational training

The study "Erhvervsuddannelse og -udvikling i landdistrikterne" (English: Vocational Training and Development in Rural Areas) shows that: (1) if rural areas want to secure skilled labour, they must make sure there are apprenticeships locally, as young people from rural areas tend not to relocate from the area where they received their training, and (2) rural areas are not all the same. Rural municipalities do a good job of retaining young skilled workers, while outlying municipalities see their skilled labourers relocate, probably due to a lack of educational opportunities or apprenticeships locally (Hedetoft, Topsø Larsen & Thomas 2020).

Higher education

Higher education in Denmark is extremely centralised. A study of the geographical distribution of enrolment in higher education amongst those admitted in 2020 conducted by Balance Denmark (a lobby group), documented that 81% attended a school in Greater Copenhagen, Aarhus, Odense or Aalborg. The seven municipalities with highest number of students (Copenhagen, Aarhus, Odense, Aalborg²⁵, Frederiksberg, Roskilde and Lyngby-Taarbæk) are also the municipalities with highest number of students per 1,000 residents.

The study shows further that despite an increasingly intense political focus on a more decentralised educational system in recent years, the trend since 2016 has been towards centralisation. Between 2016 and 2020, the number of students admitted to a higher-educational institution in the four main cities increased by 3,041. Enrolment in the rest of Denmark increased only minimally, by a total of 46.

²⁵<http://balance-danmark.dk/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Optag-2020.-Antal-uddannelsespladser-paa-de-videregaende-uddannelser.pdf>

Antal studerende optaget på en videregående uddannelse i 2020 fordelt på kommuner

Kilde: Balance Danmark • Lavet med Datawrapper

Figure 2: number of students admitted to a higher-educational programme in 2020, by municipality. Source: Balance Danmark.

The centralisation of higher-educational institutions in and around the four main cities is troublesome for large parts of the country because school-leavers tend to remain in the area where they studied. A study about attracting and retaining school leavers conducted by Damvad Analytics for University Colleges Denmark (a lobby group for schools offering professional educational programmes) concluded that 75% of school leavers still live in the municipality where they studied a year after completing their education²⁶. The study further showed that the tendency not to move away held true for students who relocated to the municipality where they studied as well as for those who lived there beforehand. More than eight out of ten students that lived in the municipality before they started their studies stay in the municipality where they studied, while roughly two-thirds of those who relocated had not moved a year after they completed their studies.

In a study of the settlement patterns of school leavers, Danish Regions (a lobby group for the five regional administrative districts) has also documented²⁷ that 80-87% of those completing university, business academy or vocational college in Greater Copenhagen still live in the Capital Region two or three years after completing their studies. At the national level, an average of 71% of school leavers live in the region in which they went to school. A number of groups have argued that decentralising education is crucial if the growth and development that education creates is to be spread evenly across the country. Each argument is accompanied by recommendations for how Denmark can ensure better educational opportunities throughout the country.

²⁶ https://issuu.com/danskeprofessionshøjskoler/docs/damvad_analyse_tiltr_kning_og_fasth

²⁷ <https://docplayer.dk/86072171-Analyse-dimittenders-bosaetning-efter-endt-uddannelse.html>

Amongst the recommendations put forward by Balance Denmark²⁸ is a proposal that the Folketing adopt a political plan and a strategy for decentralising the educational system, so that the establishment of higher-education opportunities and their placement takes place according to a thoroughly devised and comprehensive plan. Balance Denmark also proposes that the programmes offered by higher-educational institutions should to a much greater extent than is the case today be based on a regional perspective, so that educational opportunities dovetail with the skills present in individual areas. Balance Denmark further argues that there is a need for more local firms to enter into binding partnerships with educational institutions, since doing so will contribute to the educational programmes that are offered being more applicable and relevant. This, in turn, will see the establishment of apprenticeships and ensure that firms can recruit labour locally. There are good examples of binding partnerships between schools and firms in Kalundborg and Sønderborg, amongst others.

The Rural Council of Denmark (a group promoting the interests of rural areas) has proposed²⁹ that uptake caps for some higher-education programmes be adjusted to favour educational institutions outside the four main cities.

The Rural Council of Denmark proposes further that primary funding for decentralised educational programmes be increased to 2 million kroner from 4 million kroner, and that the limit capping the number of subsidies to a maximum of six educational institutions be removed. The Rural Council of Denmark recommends that the government sit an expert committee to come up with proposals for how to create more higher-education opportunities outside the four main cities that take into account the geographical recruitment needs as well as the needs of individual companies.

The Confederation of Danish Industry (DI), in its educational proposal titled "Hele Danmark skal blomstre"³⁰ (English: Let All of Denmark Bloom), calls for better opportunities for young people and adults to stay in their local area when pursuing educational opportunities. DI suggests this be done by involving municipalities and the private sector before educational programmes are moved or established, so that competencies students end up with match the needs of the local and regional labour market. In addition, DI believes that educational institutions should collaborate with local businesses to establish a common campus or collaborate in other ways that allow educational programmes to be offered jointly, rather than in isolation. DI's proposal presupposes, amongst other things, the establishment of financial incentives and subsidies that would make it attractive for the institutions to work together, and that elimination of barriers to collaboration or mergers from the relevant legislation.

Case: Residential college on Lolland-Falster

The Technical University of Denmark, Roskilde University, Guldborgsund municipality, Lolland municipality, Business Hub Zealand, Business Lolland-Falster and Fehmarn Belt Development are working together to create opportunities for teaching, research and businesses in connection with the establishment of the Fehmarn Belt Fixed Link between Denmark and Germany.

The partners plan to establish a residential college on Lolland-Falster that can provide housing for students and academics in connection with projects, courses and research. The goal of establishing a residential college on Lolland-Falster is to create an environment where students can collaborate with municipal authorities, firms, institutions and other local stakeholders to address their specific challenges and help them take advantage of the opportunities that are available to them locally.³¹

²⁸ <http://balance-danmark.dk/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Flere-uddannelser-til-hele-Denmark.-Balance-Denmark-1.pdf>

²⁹ <https://www.lanndistrikterne.dk/wp-content/uploads/sites/5/2019/04/Uddannelsesudspil.pdf>

³⁰ <https://www.danskindustri.dk/globalassets/dokumenter-analyser-publikationer-mv/pdf/opa-analyser/2021/hele-danmark-skal-blomstre---forslag.pdf>

³¹ <https://ruc.dk/nyheder/universiteter-og-lollandfalster-i-samarbejde>

2.2. Summary of position of MAP Denmark

Education and competencies have been promoted by MAP Denmark as a key element in supporting the diversification of the rural economy and rural development in general. In particular, the importance of matching educational opportunities (vocational education as well as higher education) with the needs of the labour market is emphasised, as is the need to leverage the opportunities and vocational strengths that exist locally.

There are particularly great opportunities within the green transition thanks to the range of competencies it will require. Education at all levels must, to a greater extent, be thought of in terms of the new jobs the green transition will create. In addition, rural education can help support settlement, as many stay in the area where they went to school.

As can be seen from the background section, there is a debate in Denmark about the impact and purpose of relocating educational programmes away from the four main cities. Relocation has the potential to affect another target group when placing educational institutions outside the four main cities by opening up educational opportunities to those who have either not wanted or had the opportunity to relocate. Although there are discussions between the MAP members about relocating educational programmes, there is agreement about the importance of creating a good study environment and building study environments that dovetail with vocational strengths, the needs of businesses and research opportunities if the efforts are to succeed.

In addition, it is essential for settlement in rural areas that there are primary schools, apprenticeships and secondary-education programmes. Investment in early education is highlighted in the MAP discussions as an important way to address social issues.

- MAP Denmark notes the need to study the competency value chains and the types of competencies that are needed to support development. Which value chains are there in terms of competency in relation to the new business areas in Power2X or agriculture in a perspective of lifelong learning?
- A survey of young people and the type of study environment they would like, as well as where they would like to study, is also needed.

3. Liveability: Settlement and services

3.1. Key scientific evidence

Urbanisation is still ongoing in Denmark; two trends are seen: people moving from rural areas to the largest cities, and from sparsely populated areas and smaller towns to medium-sized cities. This results in a “double urbanisation” (Ministry of Industry, Business and Financial Affairs 2020).

Figur 3.2

Udvikling i befolkningstal fordelt på byer og landdistrikter tæt på og længere væk fra de største byer, 2010-2020

Anm: Befolkningstallet er opgjort den 1. januar hvert år.
Kilde: Danmarks Statistik og egne beregninger

Figure 3: Population trends, built-up and rural areas, by distance from major cities, 2010-2020. Light blue: Built-up areas (in or close to main cities). Turquoise: Built-up areas (far removed from main cities). Black: Rural areas (close to main cities). Dark blue: Rural areas (far removed from main cities). Index: 2010 = 100. Source: Ministry of Industry, Business and Financial Affairs, 2020.

Despite the overall trend towards urbanisation, some groups can be seen moving from urban areas to rural areas, notably 30-39 year-olds (Map, next page). Members of this cohort have usually completed their education and either have established a family or are in the process of doing so. The map shows that a significant number of rural municipalities have seen in-migration, while the largest urban municipalities (Copenhagen, Frederiksberg, Aarhus, Odense, Aalborg and Esbjerg) have experienced an overall out-migration of this cohort.

Survey: transplants' motivation for relocating to Svendborg municipality

In the final quarter of 2020, Svendborg municipality recorded a surprisingly large number of transplants compared with what it had projected. The municipality found it particularly surprising that many of those relocating came from Greater Copenhagen. In order to determine why, it surveyed recent transplants and conducted follow-up interviews.

The majority of those responding to the survey were between the ages of 26 and 40, 60% were female, and two-thirds had not lived in Svendborg previously. When asked "Why did you choose to move to Svendborg municipality?", most respondents highlighted proximity to nature (66%) and proximity to water (64%). Family, culture and affordable housing were the second most common answers. Few cited educational opportunities (11%) or job opportunities (15%) as their motivation for relocating to Svendborg.

Map 1: Internal net migration of 30- to 39-year-olds 2010-2019. Source: Grunfelder et al. 2020.

Later this year, the government is expected to propose legislation promoting local access to healthcare. The cornerstones of the legislation are expected to be health centres and local hospitals that can offer emergency care in areas that are currently far removed from a hospital with an A&E.

Case study: Havtorn senior co-housing community, Ringkøbing³²

Photo: Søren Palmelund / Realdania By & Byg

The opportunity to live close to green and bluespaces, yet remain close to town. Ringkøbing town's high street and cultural institutions are less than five kilometres away, putting them within walking and biking distance. Havtorn is a new and modern co-housing community for people over 50 in Ringkøbing's Naturbydel (English: Nature Village).

Havtorn residents typically live in a unit that is smaller than their previous home. Instead, common areas are emphasised. Flats range in size from 50m² to 120 m². All have terraces or balconies that open out onto green and bluespaces. Havtorn's location on a 2 700 m² greenfield invites residents to engage in outdoor activities in the community meadow. Storage facilities enable activities such as kitesurfing, kayaking and mountain-biking. A conservatory and a common room support indoor activities.

Naturbydel is a good example of how to utilise local resources and of successful multifunctional development. The surrounding areas were prepared before construction of the first housing units began. The area was previously used as agricultural land but has been rehabilitated and now appears as a landscape that is typical of the Ringkøbing Fjord system.

All residents — both those living in the co-housing community and others living in Naturbydel — have private terraces / balconies and direct access to green and bluespaces. But, instead of looking after their own small garden plot, residents share meadows, ponds, berry patches and orchards that support activities for residents. Activities are often of an intergenerational nature.

As part of the project, a system of streams and ponds that can divert rainwater has been created. This will protect homes from the occasional flooding that can be expected as the number of cloudbursts increase. The on-going development of Naturbydel is a partnership between Ringkøbing municipality and By & Byg (Realdania's property-holding arm).

³² Description obtained at: <https://www.landsbyviden.rm.dk/temaer/cases/havtorn-bo-og-naturfaellesskab/>. Visited on 15 Sep 2021.

3.2. Summary of position of MAP Denmark

Creating attractive living conditions and supporting the social capital in rural areas is an aspect of diversification of the rural economy that MAP Denmark finds is lacking in the SHERPA Discussion Paper for the theme.

Several aspects have been emphasised by MAP Denmark as important prerequisites for supporting the development of the rural economy. Grouped under the heading "liveability", they are: settlement, new forms of housing, access to services, physical infrastructure, better utilisation of the housing stock and community.

In recent years, rural areas have received renewed focus and interest, especially as sustainability, the environment and climate have moved their way up the political and public agenda. Svendborg's survey of transplants shows that some of the reasons for relocating are lower housing prices, a desire for more community involvement and the opportunity to be closer to natural areas. This trend and narrative ought to be expanded, and it should be linked to the sustainability agenda.

Settlement has been identified by MAP Denmark as a central aspect of rural development and the foundation upon which a diversified economy can be built. Rural areas need to be attractive for people of all ages and backgrounds to settle in. Access to services needs to be a central point on the agenda when promoting rural in-migration. MAP Denmark considers schools, childcare facilities, and health services to be some of the essential public institutions and services. Services in rural areas should be adapted to meet local needs, why they can be provided in a different manner than they are in urban areas.

In addition, there is a need for expanded infrastructure in rural areas in the form of improved bike paths that improve the safety of travel and path systems that provide access to natural areas. MAP Denmark notes further the potential for the housing stock in rural areas, such as empty farm buildings, to be used in better, alternative ways.

The MAP emphasises the importance of understanding how to create good communities and a good social environment for all residents, regardless of how long they have lived there. Two municipalities worth highlighting are Lemvig and Bornholm, both of which have hired relocation consultants. Settlement efforts should involve, and be partly driven by, members of the community, but these efforts are more successful if they have the support of the municipality or other public agencies in the form of resources, advice and facilitation. Similarly, it is important to support involvement in community activities and associations in rural areas, since they are fundamental for making a place liveable.

There is growing interest in new forms of housing, be it co-housing or other types of rural communities. Alternative forms of housing, in the experience of MAP Denmark's members, appeal to city residents who are interested in changing their lifestyle and engaging with a community. This can potentially help create a more diverse rural population composition that includes people with a variety of resources.

4. Entrepreneurship

4.1. Key scientific evidence

Industry-specific growth conditions for space-intensive activities in rural areas³³

In rural areas, growth and development is often driven by a specific activity, such as agriculture and food production, tourism, shipping, fisheries, crafts or industry and manufacturing. For this reason, it is important for the development of rural and outlying areas to prioritise and improve the industry-specific conditions

³³ <https://www.landdistrikterne.dk/erhverv/>. Visited on 21 Sep 2021

necessary for the growth of space-intensive activities. Examples could be updated and bettered conditions for Danish ocean-going shippers, sensible cultivation conditions, competitive tax rates and fees for agriculture, as well as good, inexpensive and flexible transport options for the tourism industry and limiting the amount of unequal competition from publicly supported cultural institutions and sports facilities that run cafés and restaurants.

The private sector in Denmark’s rural areas contributes greatly to the national economy, and there is great potential for rural areas in the agricultural producers and manufacturers that are located there, as well as in the services sector in the form of tourism, with new and smaller companies particularly well poised. However, firms operating in the tourism industry do not find it easy to engage in the interaction between tourism and local development to find synergies, local selling points, local ownership and the like, since they are not an authority focused on local development (Bogason et al. 2020).

Taken as a whole, employment in Denmark is at a historically high level: in 87 out of the 98 municipalities, the number of those holding jobs in 2018 was higher than it was in 2013. Unemployment is low, too, but, unlike the employment figure, there is regional variation. Parts of northern Jutland, Greater Copenhagen, south-western Zealand, some island municipalities, and the four main cities in general, have a higher unemployment rate than the rest of the country.

Figure 4: Unemployment in Danish municipalities, 2013 and 2018. Source: The Government’s Regional and Rural Policy Report (2019), based on Statistics Denmark data.

Case study: Crowdfunding in Rural Areas³⁴

Development, growth and entrepreneurship require a wealth of ideas, drive and hard work. There is plenty of that in rural areas, but especially in the countryside it is difficult to attract venture capital. The “Crowdfunding i landdistrikterne” (English: Crowdfunding in Rural Areas) project is partnership involving The Rural Council of Denmark, DI and Danish Entrepreneurs (a lobby group). The project will pave the way for new financing opportunities so that entrepreneurs and start-ups can make their businesses a reality and reach their ambitions.

The project aims to illustrate how reward-based crowdfunding — a professional, but relatively unknown, financing alternative — works. Reward-based crowdfunding involves an entrepreneur raising start capital

³⁴ Description obtained at: [Crowdfunding i landdistrikterne - Landdistrikternes Fællesråd](#) Visited on 9 Sep 2021

through crowdfunding that entails selling products or services here and now, but not delivered to the investor until a later date. The model helps to address a financing need, but crowdfunding has several additional benefits: a campaign can reveal whether there is a market for a business idea, and it can motivate investors to become ambassadors by promoting the idea in a variety of ways.

To increase awareness of crowdfunding, the project work with each of the three entrepreneurs to develop professional campaigns that will launch in the summer of 2021. Experience gained from the campaigns will be gathered in a collection of on-line educational tools for use by entrepreneurs.

In addition, the project will invite municipalities, municipal business hubs and the communities where the three entrepreneurs are located to collaborate on local events focusing on entrepreneurship, funding opportunities and crowdfunding. The project will deliver policy recommendations and conclude with a conference at Christiansborg (the seat of the Folketing). The conference will serve as a forum for dialogue about improved conditions for entrepreneurship by highlighting the successes and the potential.

The project seeks to reach decision-makers as well as local entrepreneurial environments. The ambition is to ensure the best conditions for the many local idea makers and entrepreneurs who are passionate about turning an idea into a business — and to use their business to contribute to growth and development at the local level. This is a cycle that can improve an area's collective self-esteem and build up a good reputation that, in turn, can inspire more people to move to the country in seek the good life. The project received a grant from the Danish Business Authority's crowdfunding pool and took place in 2021.

4.2. Summary of position of MAP Denmark

Denmark's Planning Act establishes the guidelines for zoning, and thus where companies, housing and recreational opportunities are placed. These decisions establish the framework for local development, and MAP Denmark therefore believes that it is important to re-evaluate how the Planning Act regulates land use. Today, some non-agricultural firms experience the Planning Act as a hindrance. In some cases, this is due to regulations that prevent agricultural buildings from being used for non-agricultural purposes, or prevent disused farms from being bought by firms that are not registered as agricultural enterprises. MAP Denmark is of the opinion that it is important to look at the current regulations and evaluate whether they should be adjusted to allow activities such as energy production or greenfield housing (as detailed in the sections of this report dealing with facilitation of entrepreneurship in connection with the green transition and with relocation and long-term settlement).

MAP Denmark has observed these challenges in connection with commercial development, economic growth and rural development. One example is that financing for construction is based on property valuations, and valuations are higher within selected areas identified as growth zones.

Regulations for coastal development, a part of the Nature Conservation Act, have been identified as contributing to ensuring public access to beaches and coasts, while at the same time creating major problems, particularly for small islands.

The experience economy is another important area of commercial activity in rural areas. Especially nature has become an important parameter for a number of tourism activities, such as glamping and shelter camping. Other examples are the promotion and sale of locally produced food, gastronomic experiences and farm visits. All of these contribute to an understanding of where food comes from, provide good food experiences and further cultural awareness of a locality. As an example, many country estates have developed commercial activities such as glamping, retreat facilities, gastronomy, brewing, sporting events, natural and outdoor experiences. These are activities that cater to visitors to an area, but they are also popular with members of surrounding communities.

Partly due to the pandemic, small co-working spaces have become a topic of interest. Co-working spaces can be set up in villages, for example in parts of existing empty buildings. The pandemic has accelerated a trend brought on by digitalisation that makes some work less site-dependent. This provides an opportunity for people to relocate their workplace and to exploit a need for entrepreneurship. An expert group that features the participation of the Rural Council of Denmark is looking into locally owned businesses and entrepreneurship.

The circular economy and new forms of collaboration amongst businesses makes possible things like new forms of waste management and utilisation of various types of waste to produce new products.

Further recommendations include support for alternative forms of financing that promote local ownership, such as GreenLab. Financing can be a challenge for small businesses, but new forms of business, such as industrial clusters the likes of GreenLab, also experience it. In these cases, it is important to reach out to capital-flush companies that have a local connection for financing for new companies. In some cases, it is less a matter of a lack of capital than a lack of confidence amongst investors in new forms of financing.

- MAP Denmark recommends a thorough revision of the Planning Act to ensure better adaptation to the structure and potential of rural areas.
- Furthermore, MAP Denmark feels it is important to develop a system for alternative financing options that ensure local ownership.

5. Financing

5.1. Key scientific evidence

The “Boligfinansering i Landdistrikterne” (English: Home Financing in Rural Areas) research project looked at the challenges associated with obtaining mortgages for homes in rural areas and the polarisation of the housing market that has taken place in recent decades as home prices in urban areas have increased at a faster rate than those elsewhere (Noe et al. 2020). Most often, urbanisation is given as the reason why it is difficult to obtain a mortgage in rural areas. However, the project concludes that this cannot be the sole explanation. Instead, the problem is largely due to an increased financialisation of the housing market. Financialisation has a self-reinforcing and polarising effect on rural areas. Financialisation occurs when homes are treated as an investment object.

The authors of the report point out that if we want to change the development in rural areas, we need to get serious about addressing the self-reinforcing mechanisms of financialisation that contribute to the polarisation of the housing market into separate urban and rural markets.

The issues affecting the housing market also apply to firms. For example, agricultural enterprises experience major challenges in obtaining financing (Thorsøe & Noe 2019), but this also applies to other businesses, such as grocery stores. The financing challenges are a barrier for new companies, for example those involved with the green transition, looking to establish themselves in rural areas.

SUFISA — Sustainable Finance for Sustainable Agriculture and Fisheries (www.sufisa.eu), an EU project that ran from 2015 to 2019, examined, amongst other things, the financing challenges faced by Danish agricultural enterprises. The project also focused on ownership of Danish agricultural enterprises, including external ownership of agricultural land, which is described in more detail in the chapter on the green transition.

5.2. Summary of position of MAP Denmark

Lenders' reluctance to approve loans to buy or renovate houses in rural areas hinders development. It is not uncommon for people who want to buy or renovate a house in a rural area to have their mortgage application rejected because the house has a specific postcode. The financing problem in rural areas is a challenge for the diversification of the rural economy and hinders a change in production, and it contributes to creating a gap between urban and rural areas.

MAP Denmark finds that the problem of obtaining a mortgage is an important dimension linked to the theme of this position paper that must be addressed.

6. Digitalisation

6.1. Key scientific evidence

Well-functioning digital infrastructure is essential for running businesses, attracting residents and being able to work remotely.

To support the rollout of broadband in Denmark, a national broadband pool was established in 2016. Between 2016 and 2020, some 480 million kroner was used to make 21,000 addresses (encompassing homes, businesses and holiday homes) broadband-capable. The 2021 budget earmarks 100 million kroner for the broadband pool. Although Denmark generally has a well-developed broadband network in an international context (European Commission 2020), there are still differences in the availability and speed of broadband between rural and urban areas. The map shows the percentage of households at the municipal level that had access to a broadband connection of at least 100Mbps in 2018.

Map 2: Household access to fast broadband at municipal level. Source: Randall, Vestergård, and Meijer 2020.

6.2. Summary of position of MAP Denmark

Digitalisation is the sine qua non for rural development. A good digital connection is essential for maintaining jobs and attracting businesses to rural areas. It is essential that a fast and stable digital infrastructure is available throughout Denmark.

As Denmark was locked down during the pandemic, a large part of the population had to work from home. Increased remote working post-pandemic has the potential to create new opportunities for rural areas. Increased remote working could potentially encourage settlement in rural areas or make it possible for people to spend more time in the countryside, staying at holiday homes, for example. It is possible to imagine new constellations involving co-working spaces that would contribute to the community and the local economy.

Recommendations from MAP Denmark and Conclusions

Green transition

- It is important to ensure that the green transition contributes to rural development in the form of growth, jobs and education, and that it is generally based on local potentials and strengths. Measures to accomplish this include:
 - Developing agricultural production by introducing new products, changing soil, animal and stabling processes and creating new ownership structures that positively affects rural development.
 - Supporting co-operation and dialogue between agriculture and the local community
 - Supporting activities within the new bioeconomy that involve circular company structures and new processes based on bio-resources.
 - Contributing to locally adapted company structures by working with local firms to establish local traineeships that build on local resources.
- Make sure that land use takes into account the various interests in an inclusive manner, including the locals, by applying a holistic planning process across sectors that takes economic, social and environmental considerations into account.

Education and competencies

- Support the link between education (vocational and university-level) and the labour market.
- Build local knowledge environments and competency hubs that focus on local strengths and potentials.

Liveability: settlement and services

- Support activities that strengthen social capital in rural areas, including participation in community groups.
- Provide good, safe physical infrastructure such as bike paths and path systems that provide access to natural areas.

Entrepreneurship

- Carry out a thorough revision of the Planning Act so that it is adapted to the structure and potential of rural areas.
- Develop a system of alternative financing options that make local ownership possible and promote access to capital.

Financing

- Lenders' reluctance to issue mortgages to potential rural homeowners precludes development and should be addressed.

Digitalisation

- Continue the rollout of the digital infrastructure until everyone (households, businesses and public institutions) has fast, high quality, stable and reasonable access.

Appendix

Table 1 Compilation of noteworthy projects / initiatives / tools / methods implemented

Name	Time of implementation	Contact & Internet Address
Green transition		
Vidensportal for landdistrikterne: Energi, klima og ressourcer	2021-	Alt om energi, klima og ressourcer - Vidensportal for landdistrikter (rm.dk)
Bornholms havvind	2019-	https://www.bornholmshavvind.dk/
Liveability: Settlement and services		
Nye Naboer- mere øliv	May 2018 - May 2020	https://danske-smaaer.dk/nye-naboer/4759/ se bl.a. undersøgelse om hvorfor folk flytter til øerne: https://issuu.com/sammenslutningenafdanskesmaoer/docs/til-og-fraflytterrapport-feb.-2020-m-bilag og idékatalog: https://issuu.com/sammenslutningenafdanskesmaoer/docs/id-katalog-bos-ting
Online kursus ved Åbo akademi universitet 'Habitability'	Spring 2021	https://www.abo.fi/en/centre-for-lifelong-learning/habitability/ https://www.abo.fi/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Habitability_kurs_beskrivning-3.pdf
Tilflytterservice på Bornholm		https://xn--nstestopbornholm-uob.dk/
Vidensportal for landdistrikter: Bo- og livsformer	2021-	Alt om bo- og livsformer - Vidensportal for landdistrikter
Munksøgaard	2000-	http://www.munksoegaard.dk/index.html
Nær Velfærd (3-i-1: læge, borgerservice, IT support)	2021-2022	
Vimby, den rummelige landsby (bo- og dagtilbud, projekt støttet af Aarhus kommunes Corona-endhedspulje, arbejdsfællesskaber personer i fleksjob mm)	2012-	https://www.landsbyviden.rm.dk/temaer/cases/vimby/

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